

Pepper-potting over the Class Divide: Inclusive Social Mix or Covert Gentrification?

by Matthew W Thompson

WORD COUNT 12687
CHARACTER COUNT 72310

TIME SUBMITTED
PAPER ID

01-SEP-2011 11:44AM
11946627

University College London
Faculty of the Built Environment
Bartlett School of Planning

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Inclusive Social Mix or Covert Gentrification?

Matthew Thompson BA Hons (Oxon)

Word Count: 12,490

Being a Dissertation submitted to the faculty of The Built Environment as part of the requirements for the award of the MSc Spatial Planning at University College London:

I declare that this Dissertation is entirely my own work and that ideas, data and images, as well as direct quotations, drawn from elsewhere are identified and referenced.

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Abstract

Mixed Communities entered the UK policy arena with mixed motives. Hoping to reverse decades of growing inequality by breaking the viciously self-perpetuating cycle of spatially-concentrated poverty, the doctrine is founded on a faith that deep social divisions are to be healed with spatial interventions at the neighbourhood-scale. By investigating current best practice – ‘tenure-blind’, ‘pepper-potted’ design – this research deconstructs the claims of creating greater interaction between tenurial groups as the basis for inclusion and poverty amelioration. The findings suggest that though the latest design innovations help suppress class differences to create the surface illusion of a cohesive community, this is centred exclusively on existing shared interests, notably children. Ultimately, class antagonisms cannot be resolved by spatial proximity alone; mixed communities only prevent the emergence of class conflict necessary for a more equitable and less fractured future. This study calls for renewed engagement with class politics to challenge the structural conditions of socio-spatial inequality.

Birds of a Feather Flock Together

English proverb, c. 16th century

You can lead a horse to water but you can't make it drink

English proverb, c. 12th century

The Mixed Communities Initiative

New Labour launched the Mixed Communities Initiative (MCI) in January 2005 as a policy experiment in 12 demonstration projects located in some of the most deprived areas across the country (CLG, 2010). Predicated on the assumption that 'tenure mix' is a proxy for 'social mix' from evidence that housing tenure is closely correlated with socio-economic class (Tunstall, 2003), the MCI aimed to tackle spatially-concentrated poverty through a "more sustainable mix of housing types and tenures" (ODPM, 2005a, p.53). Part-borrowed from the US, the MCI was to tackle spiralling compound 'neighbourhood effects' seen to be exacerbating growing income inequality. By bringing the isolated disadvantaged into closer contact with broadly 'middle-class' values, policymakers hoped to instil a virtuous circle of aspiration through positive economic role models and new networks for employment opportunities. But the rhetoric of balanced inclusivity veils a revanchist agenda of urban regeneration; sparking a debate questioning the very mechanisms through which the MCI is purported to work.

Critics point to a flimsily faith-filled gap in the causal mechanism for tackling the neighbourhood effect. The MCI rests precariously upon the actual effecting of *meaningful* interaction between radically different social groups; but social theory suggests associations are sought with only others of similar social identity, and that class identity is affirmed through opposition to other classes (Bourdieu, 1984). Moreover, in using social justice arguments to legitimate the middle-class colonisation of poor inner city areas, the MCI has provoked accusations of being a covert form of state-led gentrification (Lees, 2003; Lees, 2008). Despite questions over its conceptualisation as gentrification owing to the lack of direct displacement, new-build socially-mixed 'third-wave' developments have clearly-gentrifying characteristics: capital reinvestment in previously devalourised land that upgrades the wider area's social composition and creates a landscape motivated by a demonstration of class identity (Davidson, 2007). Potential exclusionary effects of MCI developments – standing accused as 'third-

wave' gentrification – therefore need to be weighed against possible benefits for lower-income groups arising from social-mixing.

Mixed-community thinking will likely be reversed with the Localism Bill's introduction of 'Community Rights', empowering local resistance to affordable housing (CLG, 2011); but the effects of MCI developments are only just beginning to be felt, and will exercise impacts on their residents for decades to come. At the same time, socio-spatial polarisation deepens and gentrification extends its reach (Lees, 2008). The first signs of social unrest are beginning to show: the shockingly-violent riots of summer 2011 may be the first of worse to come; a harbinger of class war. The recent conservatism in gentrification research – class-cleansing attributes of 'third-wave' developments are now widely disputed – has led radical researchers to call for a re-politicised *critical* attention (Slater, 2006). In this context, it has rarely seemed more urgent to test the effects of supposedly socially-inclusive yet 'third-wave' MCI developments on fragile class relations; to critically assess what Damaris Rose (2004, p.280) calls the “uneasy cohabitation” of gentrification and social mix.

To test the MCI's greatest potential efficacy, the research examines neighbour relations in one of the most advanced examples of mixed-community thinking: Greenwich Millennium Village (GMV). This case-study represents what the MCI advocates as 'best-practice': 'tenure-blind' and 'pepper-potted' design in which social-housing and private tenures are indistinguishable and finely mixed side-by-side. A broadly ethnographic approach utilises Bourdieu's concept of 'habitus' as the lens through which to answer the driving research question:

How does MCI best practice influence cross-class interaction and perceptions to affect class relations at the neighbourhood scale?

In addressing the first objective, this study reviews existing literature and evaluates the evidence-base on mixed communities to show how the analysis of a tenure-blind pepper-potted development fills research gaps and augments our understanding of social-mixing. Second, a critical engagement with Bourdieu's

and Žižek's theories on social identity formation and class antagonism aims to construct a theoretical framework to unpack MCI mechanisms. Under the third objective, the study attempts to deconstruct the MCI fetish for spatial solutions to social problems by situating the policy in its socio-political context, revealing the underlying ideological agenda. A methodological discussion then follows that presents and justifies the empirical investigation and the case-study. Under the fourth objective, the planning background and spatial environment of GMV is assessed against the mixed-community context, uncovering any particularities of place that may influence findings. The main body of the work presents the investigation into the impacts of GMV design on residents' attitudes towards one another, focusing on how this shades perceptions of class identity in order to ascertain the health of neighbourhood-scale class relations. Finally, the study seeks to evaluate the MCI in light of conclusions drawn from findings and informed by theory. Several policy recommendations are suggested as short-term solutions with a concluding appeal for a shift in research direction that challenges the mixed-community orthodoxy.

Pepper-potting over the Class Divide: Spatial Integration as Social Solution

However admirable MCI intentions to reverse the downward spiral of poor access to social networks and public services, the MCI assumes that simply breaking-up poverty, and exposing it to middle-class lifestyles, will automatically engender opportunity and renewed social mobility. But the fundamental social mechanism around which this must pivot – the delivery of meaningful cross-class interaction – rests on shaky empirical grounds. There is limited evidence on the effects of mixed communities on social-mixing (Holmes, 2006); even ‘official’ findings from CLG suggest results are at best ambiguous (CLG, 2007, 2010). Despite the limited evidence to date, MCI projects are still in their relative infancy, and truly integrated ‘tenure-blind’ ‘pepper-potted’ developments are the rare exception, not the rule (Tunstall and Fenton, 2006). It remains unclear how these most integrated of mixed communities affect their inhabitants: something which this dissertation hopes to illuminate.

On the surface at least the MCI has never seemed more necessary. Several interconnected processes threaten to further erode social justice and civic life. Post-Fordist occupational polarisation, particularly trenchant in London’s global city economy (Sassen, 1991), has accelerated spatial segregation of groups by income, with over 1000 gated communities, for instance, sprouting up across the UK but mostly in London (Blandy, 2007). The associated trend towards the privatisation of public space, typified by the recent proliferation of Business Improvement Districts, another US export (Minton, 2009), tightens the control on people’s movement, demarcating certain spaces for exclusive tastes and consumption capabilities, thus discouraging contact between different groups. The implication is the creation of what Žižek (2009, p.91) calls “new forms of Apartheid, new walls and slums”: barricaded urban environments in which people live parallel lives.

Yet the potential of neighbourhood-based interventions to reverse growing socio-spatial divides is much disputed. Paul Cheshire (2007, 2009) dismisses the MCI for imputing too much weight to a spatial solution, treating only the symptom of the disease. Cheshire invokes the fact that residential segregation is a reflection of more general income inequality, and implores policy-makers to focus on a more traditional redistributive welfare approach that digs deeper to the root of the problem. In this vein, Lupton and Tunstall (2008) accuse the MCI of 'spatialising' and 'individualising' systemic problems, presenting disadvantaged people themselves (and the spaces they co-inhabit) as the source of their deprivation, thus distracting our attention from the structural causes of such poverty. But various thinkers have long advocated socially-mixed diverse urban environments for their socio-psychological value (Jacobs, 1960; Sennett, 1970; Young, 1990). Indeed, Lupton and Tunstall (2008, p.115) acknowledge that "mix as a system goal and mix as a regeneration tool should not be confused".

Despite these concerns, urban design research has long advocated the power of neighbourhood design to cultivate social interaction. Gehl's (1971) classic study of Danish housing schemes demonstrates how certain urban configurations are conducive to social encounters. But others note that this has yet to be fully applied to the interaction between classes (Tiesdell, 2004). Of the comparative case studies that try (Jupp, 1999; Allen et al, 2005; Bailey et al, 2006; Roberts, 2007), most focus on 'segmented' (clustered-block) rather than 'integrated' (side-by-side) layouts in the taxonomy by Groves et al (2003). But there is nonetheless promising evidence that greater tenure integration at the finer, street-level scale leads to greater interaction. Ben Jupp (1999) finds little cross-tenure mixing at estate-wide level (only 1 in 5 could name someone of a different tenure), whilst "on estates with higher amounts of street level integration nearly half knew someone with a different tenure" (1999, p11). Indeed, Tunstall and Fenton (2006, p13) concur that "literally living next door provides the best opportunity for contact between residents". This dissertation aims to investigate interaction in a context in which different tenurial classes are indeed literally living next door to one another.

Class and Consumption: the Creation of Exclusionary Spaces

A fundamental theoretical challenge to the possibility of cross-class interaction is posed by the thought of Bourdieu, whose concept of *habitus* suggests classes are defined through opposition to one another. Social identity both determines and expresses individual positioning in society, formed through the “structuring structures” of *habitus*, most simply defined as:

The array of inherited dispositions that condition bodily movement, tastes and judgements according to class position.
(Bridge, 2001, p209)

Habitus thus reproduces class identities and behaviours over time through transmitting specific socio-cultural practices. This way-of-acting-in-social-space links subjective experience to the objective structure: the interconnected *fields* of rule-based social spaces in which *habitus* is employed by actors and is in turn reproduced. Through *habitus*, different social groups, or classes, amass varying degrees of *cultural* and *economic capital*, which combine to create distinctions of taste in consumption that define one class from another. The implication is that individuals identify with class on the basis of these aesthetic distinctions, *which are themselves defined through opposition to what they are not, to other classes, to the 'other'*. In Bourdieu's words:

Each class condition is defined, simultaneously, by its intrinsic properties and by the relational properties which it derives from its position in the system of class conditions... social identity is defined and asserted through difference.
(Bourdieu, 1984, p.172).

For Bourdieu, then, the policymaker's attempts to engineer mutually-beneficial interaction between different social groups by bringing them together in one neighbourhood are vainly futile. They overlook the central feature of stratified societies:

To speak of social space means that one cannot group anyone with anyone while ignoring the fundamental differences, particularly economic and cultural ones.
(Bourdieu, 1986, p726)

Not only does spatial proximity fail to guarantee meaningful social interaction; crucially, it may rather serve to further strengthen divisions between newly-neighbouring classes. The shocking implication of Bourdieu's contention that social groups define themselves through opposition to the 'other' is that closer contact will only increase the urge to differentiate and dissociate one's social identity from that which helps define it through contrast.

For Žižek, the policymaker's denial of class antagonism is a distinctly 'middle-class' perspective, mirroring the essential core of what it means to be middle-class:

The middle-class is, in its very 'real' existence, the embodied lie, the denial of antagonism – in psychoanalytic terms, the 'middle-class' is a fetish, the impossible intersection of Left and Right which, by expelling both poles of the antagonism into the position of antisocial 'extremes' which corrode the healthy social body (multinational corporations and intruding immigrants), presents itself as the neutral common ground of Society.
(Žižek, 2000, p187)

In rejecting the Enlightenment ideal expressed in Habermasian subjectivity, Žižek contends that conflict and antagonism are an essential structuring part of our relations with others and with the Big Other of 'society' itself:

There is a subject only insofar as it is not absolute and self-grounded but remains in a tension with the impenetrable Other.
(Žižek, 2005, p142)

In denying this fundamental aspect of 'othering', the middle-class risks repressing difference and antipathy, which then seek expression through more violent means than the channels condoned by civil society. This is one possible precondition for the eruption of inner-city rioting this summer.

A more fundamental explanation lies in the changing complexities of class. The traditional Marxian class struggle between proletariat and bourgeoisie of the Industrial and even Fordist eras, appears to have been replaced by an all-encompassing consumer class: “we are all middle-class now” as Tony Blair famously declared in 1999 (Jones, 2011). Crudely speaking, the widely-accepted socio-economic accounts of post-Fordist social polarisation (Marcuse, 1989; Sassen, 1991) suggest the transition to flexible accumulation has created a growing pole of precariously underemployed, temporary low-end service-sector workers recently dubbed the ‘Precariat’ (Standing, 2011), as well as the unemployed ‘Lumpenproletariat’, which together comprise a distinct new ‘underclass’. First identified in the US by the neighbourhood effect theoriser, WJ Wilson (1987) – who posits spatial concentration and isolation as the principal cause of underclass poverty reproduction – the emergence of the British underclass can be traced back to Thatcher’s Right-to-Buy policy, which decimated the council housing stock and therefore stigmatised the dwindling minority left on state housing provision. A recent Fabian Society report (Gregory, 2009) condemns British housing policy of the past 30 years for reducing council estates to “social concentration camps” and creating in the process an “apartheid” system of housing, in which children brought up in housing association or RSL accommodation have far fewer life chances than those in the council estates of half a century ago. Whereas council housing once catered for and represented a broad cross-section of society – from the unemployed to highly-skilled workers of the ‘upper-working-class’ – the small shrinking proportion of the UK population now in social-housing neatly coincides with the rise of an underclass vilified by the media and popular opinion as ‘chavs’.

Owen Jones (2011) highlights how this ubiquitously-used term has come to describe the most underprivileged and marginalised section of society: disdainfully perceived by the middle-classes as lacking a certain “respectability”, condescendingly celebrated by the media through such characters as Little Britain’s Vicky Pollard, and targeted by politicians with the rhetoric of anti-social behaviour, ‘Broken Britain’ and ‘hoodies’. It is through the demonization of the ‘chav’ stereotype that we might see how the new middle-class expels “both poles

of the antagonism into the position of antisocial 'extremes'", thereby defining their own class identity as inhabiting the sole legitimate "healthy social body" (Žižek, 2000, p187).

Žižek's contention that middle-class identity is constructed through the denial of antagonism – dialectically defined in relation to society's extremes – suggests a certain benignity and neutrality. But this veils the active role that consumerism – increasingly marked by consumption of urban space itself – plays in the process of middle-class identity formation. Bridge suggests how middle-class consumption culture stems from a new-found reflexivity:

Whereas the dispositions of the traditional bourgeoisie are unschooled, tacit, unreflexive – the aesthetic practices of the new middle-class are public, discursive and self-conscious.
(Bridge, 2001, p211)

We can see this reflexive consumption in the stress on visibility – 'being seen' – of certain consumption settings. Middle-class *habitus* utilises certain performance spaces – a critical infrastructure of café-lined squares, restaurants, galleries and shopping arcades – that therefore act to facilitate the activities of some whilst excluding others. Middle-class identity has thus become entwined with the urban space it increasingly seeks to define in its own image. In this context, it is a near-impossible task to adequately provide in one urban space the consumption preferences that help constitute social identity for one class without alienating others.

It is on this point that the issue of gentrification enters. Key studies of classical gentrification (Butler and Robson, 2001; Butler 2003) find that groups of existing and incoming residents do not mix despite living in close proximity; and in fact, diversity of people is for the gentrifiers "valued as a kind of social wallpaper" (Butler, 2003, p.2484). It is the 'authenticity' and 'vibrancy' of the original neighbourhood itself that the middle-class colonisers appear to consume as a means to define themselves from their suburban peers in the first-wave of gentrification that began sweeping London many decades ago. Such 'consumption-gentrifiers' – early pioneers high in cultural capital but low in

economic with a commitment to authentic place-making and resentful of commodification – valorised the urban landscape, helping pave the way for ‘production-gentrifiers’, who use their ample economic capital to simply ‘buy in’ to purpose-built developments or already-gentrified neighbourhoods (Bridge, 2007).

Crudely speaking, whereas consumption-gentrifiers seek a certain level of interaction and immersion with the culture of the original inhabitants, production-gentrifiers commodify places to service their particular needs, potentially creating exclusionary spaces. Studies of ‘third-wave’ capital-led gentrification (Davidson, 2007; Davidson, 2010; Davidson and Lees, 2010) find that ‘mixed-community’ claims are often superseded by corporate objectives of attracting the so-called ‘global gentrifier class’ (Davidson, 2007; Bridge, 2007), leading to the on-site segregation of tenure groups and unsurprisingly lower levels of cross-class interaction even than in classically-gentrified neighbourhoods (Davidson, 2010).

In conceding that these social divisions are “presented, shaped, and mediated by the architecture, marketing, and built form of gentrifying developments created by real-estate developers” (p.537), Davidson also poses the corollary: that a more tenure-integrated design sensitive to social inclusion may lead to a more positive relationship between classes. Presumably, this also hinges on how the marketing and social-housing selection process determines the types and compatibilities of people tasked with forming a community. For a mixed-community to avoid class divisions, its design and marketing must be acutely sensitive to the potential of consumption spaces that express class identity to displace and exclude others.

New Labour Faith in the Church of Neoliberalism

The MCI entered the UK policy discourse under New Labour's overarching 'Urban Renaissance' agenda, which promoted dense mixed-use brownfield development as a model to revitalise our cities. The Urban Task Force's 1999 'Urban Renaissance' report laid the foundations for the Urban White Paper in 2000 and presented a "new vision of urban living"; aspiring to the 'continental attitude' of an idealised Europe, for a new-found "confidence in the ability of the city to provide a framework for humane civic life" (DETR, 1999, p.26). The very word itself, 'renaissance', and its brother-in-business, 'regeneration', connotes a process firmly fixed on reversing decay and social degeneration; promising a shiny 'revitalised' environment of boulevards and piazzas for middle-class consumption. Butler and Robson (2001) go so far as to label the Urban Renaissance as a "gentrifier's charter".

The Social Exclusion Unit's (SEU) research into "poor neighbourhoods" has diluted the middle-class bias of the Urban Renaissance with a more poverty-focused approach (SEU, 1998; Lees, 2003). The SEU was heavily influenced by the 'Neighbourhood Effect' hypothesis, first popularised in the US by WJ Wilson's (1987) landmark study. Likewise, the MCI's origins lie in policy transfer from the US; in the 1992 HOPE VI Urban Revitalisation programme (Home Ownership and Opportunities for People Everywhere), which the CLG acknowledges as "early inspiration for the mixed communities approach" (CLG, 2010, p7). Like HOPE VI, the MCI aims to tackle concentrated poverty through "redeveloping disadvantaged areas with mixed tenure and mixed income" (CLG, 2010, p19). But evidence for 'Neighbourhood Effect' derives mainly from the US, whilst UK findings are inconclusive and considered limited (Berube, 2005, Tunstall and Fenton, 2006). In light of such weak empirical foundations, the MCI appears little more than an ideological tool; what Paul Cheshire (2009) calls a "faith-based displacement activity".

In focusing on the *spatial* effects of poverty – defined by UK policy-makers as the “additional disadvantages that affect poorer people when they are concentrated in poor neighbourhoods” (ODPM, 2005b, p52) – this signalled a shift towards a thoroughly neoliberal approach first developed in the US: one which leaves market forces and associated structural inequalities untouched and engages in mere spatial re-ordering. The Department for Communities and Local Government (CLG) are explicit about this aim: “A Cabinet Office review of neighbourhood renewal argued for breaking up concentrations of deprivation, rather than simply aiming to remedy their problems” (CLG, 2010, p19). The MCI does not aim to solve inequality directly by challenging neoliberalism; but rather acts as its handmaiden to dilute and displace poverty.

An Ethnographic Enquiry

We have seen how all the positive benefits of mixed communities rely upon the contestable notion that residential proximity produces meaningful social interaction between classes. The research methodology sought to examine the empirical validity of this policy assumption through an analysis of GMV, an exemplar MCI development.

The methodological power of a single case-study approach lies in the ability to go deeper; revealing a richer account of more people's views than would be the case in a more general comparative case-study approach. The sacrifice made to representative findings that may be applied across other similar cases is balanced by the benefits reaped in analysing a very particular extreme example that in many ways embodies the principles of the MCI to a greater degree than even the 12 CLG demonstration projects (CLG, 2007; 2010). GMV was thus carefully chosen as a unique case-study widely regarded as a "showcase of best practice" in MCI design (GMV, 2010, p.4)

Of paramount interest were the more psychological aspects of social-mixing – the perceptions and attitudes towards the 'other' from both sides of the tenure divide – as it is this that determines the nature of social interaction. Apparent gaps in current social-mixing research corroborate the need for closer analysis of cross-class *attitudes*: "there has been much less research into the effects of mixed communities on values and perceptions than on more tangible characteristics such as employment status or school results" (Tunstall and Fenton, 2006, p.20). The research approach therefore takes a fundamentally qualitative look at how GMV residents with different tenures feel about each other.

The aim was to construct an ethnography that would provide a narrative account of GMV design effects on class relations. At the heart of the ethnographic approach were informal semi-structured interviews (Atkinson and Hammersley, 1994), but these were complemented by the triangulation of multiple methods so as to provide additional methodological perspectives for increased reliability

of findings (Denzin, 1970). These methods include policy discourse analysis, on-site observation, photography and formal interviewing.

Focus groups were also considered as a useful means of directly observing cross-class interaction in forums that allow residents to volunteer their opinions and interact in the process (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003) However, this method was rejected in favour of individual interviews owing to issues of representation and power imbalances that tend to distort dialogue. Social-rented units make up only 21% of GMV's total and so there was a risk that the views of lower-income residents may not be adequately heard in a forum environment. Some residents may not have felt comfortable sharing their opinions in such a formal setting, whereas informal interviews allow for all residents to give their views more freely, without fear of repercussions in the community.

Individual unstructured interviews were thus deemed the fairest and most amenable method to ensuring the fullest representation of both private-owners and social-housing tenants. These interviews were conducted in an open-ended manner in order to allow respondents to direct the conversation as far as possible to reveal underlying attitudes. Opening and prompt questions were designed to keep the interview on topic but to be as general and as least leading as possible. Interviews were attained through two methods: door-to-door and street interviews. Both approaches were conducted completely at random in various locations throughout the entire development. A total of 20 of those approached agreed to interview: four social-housing tenants, a GMV employee, the rest private-owners or renters. A further formal interview was conducted with a Policy Planner at Tower Hamlets Borough Council, providing a professional perspective.

Interviews were conducted in 4 days of on-site research, representing a diverse range of times of day and week. On-site observation aimed to capture the full variety of GMV life: from school opening/closing times, 'rush hours', leisure periods, to quieter times; illustrated through photography.

The ethical considerations of the research were limited owing to the avoidance of any particularly intrusive approaches. Several measures were taken, however, to ensure that all interview respondents were treated ethically. First, all interviewees were made to understand that their response to questions was voluntary; second, that interviews were completely confidential and anonymous, with neither name nor address made public.

GMV: a Tale of Two Villages

GMV sits at the heart of the Greenwich Peninsula on the site of what was Europe's largest gasworks (GMVa, 2010). Started in 1999, with the first residents in December 2000, there are now 1095 completed homes and another some 1800 planned for future phases. The development is the flagship project for the wider Greenwich Peninsula redevelopment, which involves the remediation of 121 hectares and total planned construction of over 10,000 homes on what was some of the UK's most contaminated ex-industrial land. The Greenwich Peninsula Masterplan was designed by the Urban Renaissance tsar himself, Richard Rogers (GMV, 2005), reflecting how the area is the product of New Labour ideology: a "Blairite tabula rasa" (Hatherley, 2010, p299). The hollow positivity and aspirational individualism of the era is encapsulated by Greenwich Peninsula's tagline (fig.1).

Figure 1: Greenwich Peninsula Tagline

The colouring-in of the GMV part of the blank slate is overseen by a public-private partnership, Greenwich Millennium Village Ltd (GMVL), headed by the old QUANGO English Partnerships, in conjunction with developers Taylor Woodrow and Countryside Homes, and in association with Moat Housing Group. The New Labour love-affair with 'stakeholder management' and the contracting-out of services is embodied in the 'representative' GMVL Management Board and their appointment of a private-sector company, Pinnacle as the management agents, and who in turn have put various site-management contracts out to tender.

GMV is highly-regarded in urban design circles, having won some 30 awards, including the first UK EcoHomes 'excellent' rating and CABI's Building for Life gold standard (GMV, 2010b, p4). Many of these awards celebrate its green credentials: sustainable development that includes provision of a CHP system and on-site Ecology-park (fig.2). But it is made clear that "sustainable development is as much about establishing an inclusive society as it is about brilliant design and innovative architecture" (GMV, 2011). It thus has "everything a community needs to grow": amenities that include a primary school, health centre, residents association, and public square lined with various shops and leisure facilities (fig.3). Most importantly, GMV boasts a pepper-potted tenure layout with affordable units of indistinguishable tenure-blind design (GMV, 2010a).

Figure 2: Ecology-park boardwalk

Figure 3: Village-square advert

Figure 4: Map showing GMV phases.

The reality, however, falls short of these principles. Of the original phase coloured brown in fig.4 above (the largest section in yellow are future phases yet to be built), only the southern section, south-west of the central playing fields, designed by Proctor-Matthews, is strictly pepper-potted development. This is a mixture of low-rise intricate terraced housing (fig.5) and denser perimeter block flats (fig.6)

Figure 5: First-phase terraced-housing

Figure 6: First-phase perimeter-block flats.

The northern section of the original phase, overlooking the river and Ecology-park (mostly light blue in fig.4) is a group of dense, relatively-high-rise flats that, despite their progressive-hinting Dutch-style design (fig.7) contain only some affordable housing on the ground floor, but otherwise privately-owned/rented. This is a far cry from the original principles of radical mixing. It is tragically ironic that the design – admittedly compromised after his death in 2005 – was Ralph Erskine's, the architect of the last great public housing scheme interrupted by Thatcher in 1981 (Hatherley, 2010, p.294). Might this foretell the fate of GMV?

Figure 7: First-phase Erskine flats

The last two phases to be built (orange and blue in fig.4) designed by the Erskine successor firm, Tovatt and John Robertson Architects, are blocks of flats in a similar-but-boxier style to the original Erskine buildings, and likewise cannot claim a pepper-potted degree of integration: social-housing tenants are concentrated together on the ground floor. The final phase, Metcalfe Court (blue in fig.4) provided ground-floor retail units framing a new village-square (fig.8)

Figure 8: Village-square framed by final-phase flats.

Despite meeting the planning requirement of 30% affordable housing, the provision of only 21% social rented against 9% shared ownership and 70% private (GMV, 2010b, p3) is surprisingly low for an exemplary mixed-community. This reflects the fact that many of the large blocks of flats are

predominantly private units, with some areas of the village, particularly the first-phase terraced housing, exhibiting much higher proportions of much more finely mixed social-housing. GMV is split into two entirely different character areas: the pepper-potted 'villagey' terraced-housing to the south; and the mostly-private flats overlooking the river, lake and village-square.

Figure 9: Unfinished surroundings.

For all its 'sustainable community' aspirations, GMV is caught between an out-of-town retail park made up of DIY stores and a "sustainable" Sainsbury's with token wind-turbine, and an entertainment megaplex dominated by the Dome and other post-architectural tents like the David Beckham Football Academy (fig.11). GMV sits awkwardly amid a desolate wasteland parcelled into plots by blue fencing, promotional billboards, prohibitive signs and surveillance cameras: empty land preparing for the next speculative property boom (fig.9). On one of his more recent psycho-geographical rambles, Iain Sinclair describes it thus:

Hard to decide, as CCTV cameras swivel, if it's an English Guantanamo or a car boot sale waiting to happen...the Dome exclusion zone is a notable addition to the downriver micro-climate: spears of grass breaking through the tarmac, artworks degrading into their industrial origins. Toy-town estates in primary colours laid out in contradiction of everything that envelops them.
(Sinclair, 2011, p206)

Figure 10: Jarring juxtaposition.

Figure 11: Two white tents

The cheerful child-like rendering and artificiality of GMV's architecture (fig.10) connotes the "compulsory celebration" demanded by the unavoidable Dome, with "yellow candlesticks stabbed into icing sugar" (Sinclair, 2011, p.206). Perhaps the relative isolation, except for the excellent tube connection to Canary Wharf and easy access to the O2 Arena, prefigures GMV as a commuter-town for bankers with a sweet-tooth for chain restaurants, blockbuster films and superstar concerts, all under one roof? Yet a central part of the GMV 'brand' is sustainability; and so these production-gentrifiers are likely accompanied by "people who wanted to be pioneers in an environmentally sensitive development" as well as socially-aware groups who value 'inclusivity' (GMV, 2010a, p.4).

The allusion to an 'urban village' (fig.12) and inevitable association with the hyper-gentrified Greenwich Village in New York suggest a clientele searching for a made-to-order 'trendy' lifestyle. The 'Millennium' in the name cannot help but conjure parallels with the quasi-fictional Chelsea Marina in Ballard's 'Millennium People'; an image prefixed by the similar new-build riverside setting (Ballard, 2003). Like, the middle-class enclaves in Ballard's fiction, GMV is cut-off from the surrounding city – albeit by empty wasteland rather than fortified gates – and so seems to turn inwards. Might the comparison stretch to the discovery of Ballardian psycho-pathologies and class tensions seething beneath neighbourly life?

Figure 12: Branding the 'Village'

As if sensing this anomic potential, early attempts were made by GMVL to give residents a stake in the village and foster community life. Funds were made available for the Moat Community Development Manager “with a remit to act as a catalyst for community activity...across tenures” (GMV, 2010a, p4). The Manager helped set up a residents association, the Greenwich Millennium Village Association (GMVA), to which membership is automatic to all GMV residents. An internally-appointed committee oversees GMVA, whose role is to work “to build a village community, to represent the interests of residents and to promote the recognition of residents' rights.” (GMVA, 2011) A community website, owned and administered by the GMVA Committee, acts as an online residents' Forum where “local news and views can be exchanged within a secure environment” (GMVA, 2011).

Community life means more than just a stake in a virtual environment. Caroline Field, the former Moat Community Development Manager, explains how the Arts Initiative gave residents a say in the visual identity of the village itself:

As the entire scheme majors on areas of public open space, GMV decided against simply 'buying in' standard pieces of art or sculpture. Instead they chose to create a community forum by inviting residents to get together and, after seeing various on-site exhibitions by specially chosen artists, the brave step was taken to allow all residents to negotiate between themselves and pick the winning artists to design public artwork in which they have all been involved.

(Press release, 10/03/06, GMV, 2011)

Figure 13: Community Art fronting the School.

Community art, regardless of debates over its aesthetic merits (fig.13), cannot by itself keep people engaged. Over a decade has now passed since the original tenants helped commission such work and many new faces will have replaced the old. The Moat Community Development Manager was active for only 2 years and after this initial boost-start to community life, it remains to be seen how integration proceeds without such assistance.

One long-lasting anchor of community life has been established with the on-site Millennium Primary School (fig.13; located at GMV's western corner). The school, which was partly re-constituted from the local closure of another, was pivotal in Moat's social-housing lettings plan. Target groups included disadvantaged families with children moving to the new primary school, which therefore served as a common focal point for many residents. Designed to be a 'community hub', the school is thus a natural meeting-point for parents, but for those without

children, alternative infrastructure, such as a community centre, is lacking: posing the question of whether GMV's community life in any way transcends its school?

Mixed Commitments

The first thing to strike me upon meeting residents was the almost-unanimous approval of place. This was most marked in the social-housing tenants, who tended to emphasize the attractiveness of the surroundings: “it’s really peaceful and lovely...the ecology-park with the ducks. I just love it all”. Such enthusiasm seemed to arise through contrast with previous experience; another tenant remarked:

“I’ve seen a lot of shit holes out there brother. There ain’t no fuckers spraying walls here...no 20 people with their cars out mechanicing them, you know; no shit in their front gardens.”

Figure 14: Rural Tranquillity

Some private-owners/renters enthused on the ecologically-innovative design and the tranquillity in spite of being so close to London (fig.14). Many were more ambivalent, non-committedly acknowledging the commuting convenience:

"It was just, umm, a good estate near to the tube and pretty convenient really... It takes me two hours to get to work so being close to the tube was pretty important"

Indeed, this lack of commitment to place seemed to characterise middle-class residents, several of whom bought a home without any knowledge of the local area or having even visited the site: "I was promised a room with a view so I booked a place off plan" admitted one owner. The habitus of buyers in GMV accords with what Bridge (2007) identifies as production-gentrifiers: busy professionals who 'buy-in' to a convenient or fashionable location and use their home almost as a 'crash-pad' for their hectic schedules mostly based in central London. Though not as highly-mobile as the 'global gentrifier' class, who tend to have international horizons, these gentrifiers do not grow deep roots in one specific place but make roving use of the entire city. As one private-renter summarises:

"I think these days that everyone is so busy with their own lives that you just like do your own thing and get on with it, and because London is so big you're spread out across the whole city and you just meet in the middle somewhere convenient for everyone...I don't hang out with the neighbours, but the people on that side, a Japanese lady, we have cocktails together"

The full extent of community interaction for this particular person is a few cocktails with one next-door neighbour. This highly-mobile and individualistic habitus is fairly representative of GMV private-renters and even prevalent among some home-owners. It became clear that the habitus of this class in no way overlaps with that of their social-housing neighbours.

The development of amenities catering specifically to mobile lifestyles reflects the dominance of this populous group. The CGI-adorned windows of the empty retail units (fig.15) proclaim the kind of lifestyles the 'new homes coming soon' might facilitate. In a scene reminiscent of the Urban Renaissance call for

continental café culture: cappuccino-sipping is ritualised by the chattering classes whilst a laptop sits open on a café table; an official endorsement of gentrification.

Figure 15: Visions of an Urban Renaissance?

There is no room for anything outside the commodified or upmarket; nothing resembling a local pub, take-away, charity-shop, butchers, bakers, or bookmakers. Instead, the village-square includes only those essential services for the time-constrained office-worker: a chain 'Nisa Local' foodstore, pharmacy, dry-cleaners, estate-agents and an 'Ayurveda Pura' Health Spa & Beauty Centre, with an adjoining 'Café Pura'. No sign of a mixed-community here.

The health-spa and café (fig.16) are the perfect embodiments of the 'production-gentrifier' lifestyle: a standardised service that offers luxurious beauty treatments, yoga classes and holistic therapies for those with high economic capital to afford fashionable express de-stressing.

Figure 16: Reflections of Exclusivity.

Figure 17: Gourmet Tastes

The Café (fig.17), which uses the same entrance as the spa, specialises in vegetarian health foods yet is the village’s only on-site space to socialise over food and drink. The café’s ‘baristas’ revealed that it was mostly used by “Mums after they’ve dropped their kids off at the school”, otherwise by “young people in their 30s who use the Spa”, but gets “pretty quiet during the day” (fig.18). Despite high demand among respondents for more social facilities, such as a pub or community centre, GMV has failed to provide diverse or inclusive enough social amenities.

Figure 18: Mums enjoying a coffee

Figure 19: The school run begins.

Child-centricity

The quietude in GMV was evident at almost all times, save for school pick-up periods (fig.19). Then, the square was transformed from a windswept vastness traversed by the odd lone villager, into a vibrant urban space filled with children playing. Indeed, the school plays a fundamental role in bringing the various people of GMV together and infusing life into its streets. An owner-occupier of a terraced house explained:

"The children can play outside, there's a great community atmosphere. My son was at the primary school...he used to have 4 friends in the local area...I know some [social-housing tenants] through the school a little bit...through my kids I do mix with various people"

Children provide a bridge between people. A social-housing tenant likewise remarked that she knows "lots of people at the school even though my daughter goes to school somewhere else". Even when the school is not directly implicated, its presence seems to bring different classes in contact through having something so fundamental in common.

But not everyone has, or indeed wants, a child. In partly sewing up the divide between parents of different backgrounds, the school has inadvertently created a new schism, succinctly stated by one flat-dweller: "I think if you've got kids at the school there is a community atmosphere but I don't have kids." The sentiment is elaborated by a home-owner, who teaches locally:

"The square is beginning to get people together...but we still don't have a place to go, you know a community centre we can use; not everyone wants their focus around children. I teach so, you know; but there's an assumption there. Having said that, it wouldn't be a community without the school and children....it would be like a commuter land."

GMV planners seemed bent on warding off this danger in their noticeable bias for families. Street signs celebrate their rightful inhabitants (fig.20); the visitor-centre of the Ecology-park - GMV's 'sustainability' centrepiece - is geared towards the education and entertainment of children (fig.21).

Figure 20: Child Lane

Figure 21: A Sustainable Education?

This unforeseen social cleavage appears to correlate with a spatial divide running through the development. Those in the terraced housing nearest the school tend to be families, whilst those in the flats around the square and riverside are mostly young-professionals. On the terraced side, there appears to be more of a community life going on – albeit centred on children – whilst the flats are marred by solitude and transience. A Mother privately-renting in Metcalfe Court exclaimed:

“We’ve been here for two years, and the people next door to us have changed three or four times! Its usually people sharing”

The fast-turnover mirrors the fast-paced, transient lifestyles of young-professionals focused on their careers. But this is also the result of a speculative ‘buy-to-let’ sales approach. Although the “developer made the decision not to sell units to bulk purchasers, as this can lead to an over-concentration of properties bought to let out”, it is nonetheless publicly conceded that “this does happen at GMV” (GMV, 2010a, p2). The lamentable consequences of this short-termist approach were spelled out to me by a young flat-dweller:

"We've got a flat that overlooks the Ecology-park. But in terms of community, it's massively lacking. I don't know whether it's due to living in flats and stuff, but people rarely talk to one another, which is a real shame. Everyone keeps themselves to themselves, people don't even talk across balconies out the back. Where we are it's really, really quiet; there seems to be quite a lot of business people living in these flats as well; I don't know whether they go away at weekends, but it seems mostly absent professionals"

This tenant's experience of the very private and individualistic habitus of her neighbours suggests that parts of GMV have indeed become the anaemic 'commuter land' the teacher feared from the absence of children. Very little interaction was reported between residents of the flats (mostly constituting polite acknowledgements), and even less was meaningful (social exchange perceived as a human relationship). Flat-renters reported almost no interaction with social-housing tenants.

The contrast in community life with the other side of GMV – the terraced streets – could not be more striking, as this social-housing tenant makes clear:

I know everyone in the courtyard at the back, there's a nice mixture; I've got fantastic neighbours. I know everyone here across my street, it's an encapsulated bubble; but you go over there towards the shops, I don't get to talk to people much.

This man's feelings express a definite sense of belonging in his immediate, street-scale environment. The sociable 'bubble' bursts upon nearing the shops, which demarcate the boundary between terraces and flats. The main ingredient in the mixing of neighbours is alluded to in his referencing the "courtyard at the back". These communal gardens sit at the centre of each perimeter block of terraced-housing, and most blocks of flats, except the Erskine flats overlooking the lake and the final-phase on the square's eastern side.

Figure 22: The New Gated Gardens of London

To the outside observer, these cloistered environments give the impression of a gated community: a strictly private and highly-securitised zone enticing the outsider with the forbidden allure of sheltered greenery (fig.22). A private-renter of a flat with access to a communal garden enthused how they were “just like the gated gardens of Georgian London”. But unlike these exclusive playgrounds of the 19th century upper-classes, GMV’s contemporary versions, although similarly for the sole use of residents, are inclusive spaces for both rich and poor. They provide a safe and highly-social space for tenants, owners and their children to

interact across class lines. They may be the village's saving grace. One GMVL employee certainly seems to think so:

"In the flats, most people don't even know their next door neighbour, but here with the communal gardens, it's more social. I look after the gardens and there're children playing together in the gardens and the tenants get to know each other"

In a role self-described as the village's 'caretaker', his unique experience of directly observing the life that goes on behind closed garden gates provides the basis for an informed assessment: that these gardens are fundamental in facilitating interaction. It is difficult to infer how much of this socialising amounts to *cross-class* interaction, but we must recall how one social-housing tenant "know[s] everyone in the courtyard at the back", at the same time that "there's a nice mixture". The blanket enthusiasm for his neighbours, who are mostly private-owners, suggests some cross-class interaction, or at least some positive influence on attitudes towards the 'other'. With similar sentiments expressed in the terraces by other social-housing tenants, communal gardens play a central role in encouraging cross-class neighbourliness, complementing pepper-potting to form a dual-approach.

Communal gardens appear to have a powerful effect even in non-pepper-potted blocks. More sociability, though not necessarily cross-class interaction, was reported in flats with communal gardens than in the flats without. The three spatial zones of differing combinations – pepper-potted-terraces with gardens; flats with gardens; and mono-tenure flats without – appears to broadly correlate with differences in perceived levels of cross-class interaction and relative positivity towards the other.

Ironically, the provision of such internally-cohesive and close-knit blocks in one section of the site seems to have fostered an inward-looking 'bubble' mentality that has as its corollary hostility towards the other side. The 'us and them' culture that usually divides classes has been transferred to a spatial rift: between two different designs catering for different housing needs, families and young-professionals. One owner of a terraced-house revealed:

"There's a lot of snobbery with the private-owners, especially over in the flats, saying that people from Moat are the ones that cause problems. I don't think that's really true"

Although she admits that there is a general tension between social-housing tenants and private-owners, she sees this as mostly emanating from the flats. She distances herself from these residents by gesturing and emphasizing the flats as "over" there; siding with her Moat neighbours in the terraces. One of her Moat neighbours, sharing the same garden, also makes this distinction between 'here' and 'over there':

"I've been living here 10 years, and you get to know certain people, but there's certain divides here. There's a them and an us...a stone's throw away, up there [gesturing] up there...people are paying 270 odd grand for their houses. Then there's the million pound apartments. People paying that sort of money do not want social-housing next to 'em...People get proper pissy...once you get in your front door you just close it behind you. There's that sort of attitude"

This view does not acknowledge any divisions with immediate neighbours, channelling all hostility towards those in expensive apartments, too distant to really get to know. There is an implicit acceptance of a negative perception of social-housing in automatically assuming people in the flats consciously avoid living near. This negative conception of the other's attitude towards oneself possibly derives from a defensive self-assessment bound up in social judgements on one's own class.

Other social-housing tenants also exhibited an awareness of derogatory stereotypes of their self-identified class:

"Actually we don't sit on our bottoms on benefits all the time. There are choices. Children need to see that actually so-and-so's got a really nice car because they go out to work; that's why they've got really nice things...they need to see the pathway there"

In taking the time to dispel the myths, this tenant shows a strong desire to distance herself from crude class depictions. She parrots the 'neighbourhood

effect' rationale for the MCI, having internalised the neoliberal dogma that poverty is a choice of the individual. But how much of her staunch defence of middle-class role-models was formed from observations of GMV? This distinctly aspirational outlook – held by many social-housing tenants – may rather amount to a pre-conceived attitude that helped secure a home in the Moat selection process. Despite inclusive design, might gentrification be operating at the marketing and tenant-selection stage, ensuring only those with aspirational values conducive to middle-class consumption come to reside in GMV?

Virtual Bullying

Despite pepper-potted communal gardens, internal antagonisms are nevertheless present. One terraced-house-owner whose “next door neighbours are from Moat”, admitted:

“The only slight downside is that they do have to have a certain amount of people on social-housing. I mean most of them are fine...but generally the kids are unruly and any loud noises...I mean, as a generalisation...there are many people who think like that around here but they would be too scared to say...people do mention it on the forum and get blown apart”

This man felt clearly uncomfortable confiding his views on the ‘other’. Why are people “too scared” to speak up on the GMVA internet forum? Might this suggest a socially-enforced public conviviality between classes that discourages and represses the expression of underlying class tensions?

The intriguing thing about GMV class relations is the unprecedented influence of the GMVA internet forum. A young renter without a garden lamented:

“I joined (the forum) ‘cause I wanted to find out how to get a plumber to fix my loo. I haven’t actually talked to anyone engaged in it but it just seems to be a lot of people who’ve lived here for a long time complaining about a lot of rubbish, so it’s not really inclusive...I’ve never felt like I could join in with it...These people have been here for a long time and they’ve said they’ve seen a demise in the area, that there’s a lot more anti-social behaviour”

This demonstrates the power of the internet to forge a community across a site that is arguably too segregated to ordinarily cohere. But it also hints at the exclusionary potential of power relations exerted through this medium. According to her, GMVA is dominated by long-standing home-owners who present an intimidating barrier to participation. One home-owner of 7 years, who was “pretty much here when it all started”, corroborates this evaluation:

"I used to be on the forum but it became a forum for complaining and I got tired of listening to it so I withdrew; just a lot of people whingeing: 'this one's made too much noise, and this one's hanging out of the window'"

These accounts imply that the forum plays host to class-based bullying. The complaints of "too much noise" sound strikingly familiar: echoing the views that the terraced-house owner ascribed to people "too scared to say" anything, yet who strangely find their voice in the secure confines of the forum, immune from face-to-face accountability.

But the forum does have a physical incarnation. The GMVA holds regular community meetings, illuminated by one home-owner's experience:

"I went to one meeting. That's where I got the message that they're a bit sort of anti-Moat, and a friend of mine who is in Moat housing thought she couldn't go to these community meetings; I said 'well yes you can, they want people to represent Moat there'...She made a film on the building of Millennium Village....she showed her film and tried to get things organised, but she also went to one of those meetings and felt that she wasn't accepted there...They talk an awful lot but not much is done; the usual thing"

The Moat resident's feeling unwelcome at GMVA meetings suggests a tacit understanding that social-housing tenants are deemed mere second-class citizens of GMV. The fact that this tenant was so proactive and community-spirited in shooting and showing a documentary on the very creation of GMV, only to feel snubbed by members of its community association, demonstrates the deep-seated prejudice against Moat residents.

Tenure-visible Antagonisms

A remarkable aspect of class relations was the notable absence of conventional class terms in residents' responses. Few referred to themselves or others as 'working-class' or 'middle-class', and never used the more loaded term 'chav'. In their place is identification with housing tenure as a euphemism for class. Almost all residents spoke of "Moat people", "people on social-housing", "private-owners", or "young-professionals", the latter outwardly focusing on age and employment status but denoting private-renters. It is as if tenure status has subsumed class identity in GMV, or else used as shorthand. By categorising residents by their housing, people are automatically stigmatised regardless of how their aesthetic values and lifestyles define them. GMV residents appear hyper-aware of housing definitions, probably owing to the public promotion of a socially-inclusive mixed-community. Ironically, by making this aim so explicit, the labels themselves have taken on an unforeseen power of their own; in line with Labelling Theory (Goffman, 1959) residents are starting to conform to the identities connoted by these categories.

Figure 23: Indistinguishable design

The effects of tenure-blind pepper-potting in countering this tendency appear to have largely failed. Despite impeccable design efforts to make social-housing look identical to private homes (fig.23), many private-owners were quick to point out differences. The following is indicative:

"I mean without sounding too snobbish, you can spot the people who probably don't own their houses: shopping trolleys outside, that kind of thing"

Tenure-blind housing has not only failed to prevent the identification of tenure, but may even have facilitated it through providing a blank canvas on which subtle differences in treatment leave an indelible mark. Indeed, the home plays a fundamental part in a distinctly middle-class habitus, originally deriving from the bourgeois fetish for property (Bourdieu, 1984). This might be especially true in a culture obsessed with property ownership; in which an 'Englishman's home is his castle'. In our reflexive age where social identity is increasingly dependent on the performative display of consumption (Bridge, 2001), the pressure to present the home as an essential part of self-identity has possibly never been more keenly felt. Socially-engineered design cannot hope to quell the urge to make a home one's own.

Individuation in home presentation was evident throughout GMV as fig.24 demonstrates, particularly in the terraces where external personalisations are made easier by exclusive entrances. Draconian rules issued by Pinnacle, the site agents, might have helped ensure the requisite level of visual homogeneity, but these appear to be rarely enforced, eliciting only baffled bemusement from one home-owner:

"You can't really do anything to the outside without asking permission, then they have funny rules like you're not meant to have garden sheds, but they don't really follow them up"

Figure 24: Varied personal tastes

Behind observations of superficial differences – like distaste for “shopping trolleys outside” – there lurks a pernicious attitude towards certain social-housing tenants. Their behaviour and activities were the features most remarked upon by middle-class residents when commenting on differences. Some went as far as to impersonate tenants:

“They’ll be the mums who swear at the kids and say: ‘oi you fucking come in side!’”

The GMVA forum was said to be dominated by general complaints about “people playing music, kids hanging out”. But much of this was focused on Metcalfe Court, where successive groups of social-housing tenants have been housed together on the first-floor overlooking the village-square. The GMV caretaker helped shed some light:

"They have a notorious estate in Eltham, the Fourier Estate, and they condemned it, and unfortunately they brought the tenants from there over here and housed them all together in Metcalfe Court. We had a lot of drug problems, a lot of drug dealers. I had a friend who sat on the committee, then they all got moved on, 15 of them, and we haven't seen them since. That improved it a lot."

The concentration on one floor of tenants with a distinct habitus developed in a particularly disadvantaged estate invites a micro-neighbourhood-effect explanation for these problems. It also hints at how middle-class perceptions of social-housing may have been negatively distorted. Would these tenants have behaved differently if housed separately, mixed with other residents in the pepper-potted part of GMV? We will never know. Perhaps to safeguard the success of GMV's pioneering pepper-potted blocks, Moat carefully selected tenants that would best integrate and least antagonise the middle-class buyers that were essential to GMV's financial viability? The most disadvantaged of tenants – supposedly to benefit most from integration – were clustered together out of fear of their "notorious" backgrounds and then moved on when the prophecy unsurprisingly self-fulfilled. This mass-eviction is none other than officially-sanctioned gentrification: the displacement of those who jar with the prevailing middle-class habitus.

This creeping gentrification is part of a wider problem. GMV is an oasis in a desert of future speculative development that will exert pressures for a more exclusive habitus. The dangers were spelled out in an interview with ex-GMV-resident and senior policy planner at neighbouring Tower Hamlets Borough Council:

"The developments being built around it along the river are already 80% owned by private investors for Canary Wharf workers to rent, so the area will become infiltrated by City Boys, and I suppose they'll shop in the local shops, which'll bring some money in, but other than that they'll be no interaction...If there're no connections between GMV and these developments, there'll be no sense of place, and all efforts at wider place-making will have failed."

Although inconsistencies in GMV's design have engendered internal divisions, the efforts to build a community - notably in the provision of pepper-potted housing around communal gardens - have helped bridge class differences where they were fully applied. But even if such design innovations were implemented consistently throughout, this flawed example of best practice cannot hope to reverse the trends towards gentrification of a landscape in orbit of the City.

The Denial of Antagonism in an Atomised Age

GMV is the archetypal yet atypical MCI development. Its uniqueness as a self-conscious pioneer has partly distorted its class relations, with an unusual hyper-awareness of housing tenure among residents highlighting a divide between private-renters and social-housing tenants. GMVA meetings and the innovative online forum have acted against original intentions to facilitate the middle-class exclusion of social-housing tenants from community life. Design has not prevented class antagonisms developing out of the oppositional process of 'othering' which Bourdieu claims to underpin self-identity, and which Žižek celebrates as the essence of inter-subjective existence.

But this is a tale of two villages. Tenure-blind pepper-potting and communal gardens have not been provided throughout. Where they have, a more open dialogue between classes has developed. In their absence, neighbours hardly interact at all and lead highly-individualistic, private lives. Tenure-blind design has not hidden but rather heightened sensitivity to class differences: the propensity described by Bourdieu to make aesthetic distinctions through opposition to the 'other' has only been intensified. Pepper-potting and communal gardens, however, have enabled interaction between otherwise-self-segregating groups, helped break down some class prejudices, and even produced some friends among neighbours.

It nonetheless remains difficult to disentangle the effects of pepper-potted communal gardens from the sociable habitus of families. Instances of cross-class mutuality were shown to rely heavily on the single shared interest of children. The primary school acts as an anchor around which diverse parents can meet each other, and this commonality is carried over into neighbourly relations. The irreconcilable differences in lifestyle between families and highly-mobile renters have led to spatial separation. This laid the physical foundations for a greater schism between young-professionals and social-housing tenants. Ultimately,

there is an inherent contradiction in the notion of mixed communities in such a diverse society. The MCI assumes that simply bringing people together in one place automatically creates a common community; “that spatial proximity somehow engenders the creation of a people” (Davidson, 2010).

A deeper societal problem pervades. In his novel, ‘Atomised’, Michel Houellebecq (2001) denounces the generation of 1968, “les soixante-huitards”, who by achieving socio-sexual liberation have left us with a mutant strain of selfish-individualism and lifestyle-libertarianism. In revolting against the tendency of bureaucratic-capitalism to create “one-dimensional-man”, Herbert Marcuse’s (1964) dark prophecy has emerged in sublimated form. Capitalism has cleverly accommodated the myriad desires of middle-class self-expression by commodifying anything that helps define this new individuated self. The old belongings of nation, religion, class, community and family that bequeathed meaning have been replaced by an empty consumerism, predicated on brutal competitiveness and hyper-individualism. But whilst the middle-classes enjoy access to the legitimate means of consumption, others remain completely disenfranchised. The ‘mindless violence’ of the summer riots reflects frustration with a system that both whips up irrational desires and denies their satisfaction; a nihilistic expression of the lack of any meaningful choice in a system apparently saturated with choice. Is it so surprising that inclusive design does not automatically create a community out of atomised individuals? The dim glimmer of a mixed-community emerging in GMV’s family-focused communal gardens provides some hope. Perhaps this is testament to the power of children to unite individuals around the only remaining bastion of meaning (Houellebecq, 2001): “the last unit separating the individual from the market”.

In the quest for community, GMV focused too many of its design efforts on families. The highly-individuated young-professionals that constitute most of the development seem no more integrated here – with each other or with other classes – than in the deeply-divided riverside developments researched by Davidson (2007, 2010). Even in the absence of integration, young-professionals have nonetheless gentrified parts of GMV. The creation of exclusionary spaces of

consumption in the Village-square that serves the gourmet-tastes of production-gentrifiers both excludes poorer residents and entices them with a visible symbol of material aspiration. But mixed communities cannot simply make all residents middle-class by fostering an aspirational culture. Accelerating inequalities are leaving a substantial section of society behind without the means to engage in the new middle-class habitus, however unsatisfactory and devoid of meaning. But we cannot go on displacing those who do not comply with our consumption-based social contract. It is clear that a mixed-community by itself cannot peacefully accommodate the middle-class and the disenfranchised poor.

At its heart, the MCI is “the embodied lie, the denial of antagonism” (Žižek, 2000, p.187). Class antagonisms are not merely disagreements over aesthetic tastes; they structure the process of ‘othering’ that is the source of the individual subject. Pepper-potting over class differences is a misunderstanding – a denial – of the inherent value of conflict. Richard Sennett (1970) convincingly argues for the value of direct confrontation with ‘otherness’ as an essential component in psychological growth and the development of a mature shared social consciousness. But the MCI does not facilitate conflict and debate; it rather represses difference, leaving antagonisms festering beneath neighbourly pleasantries. A debate needs to be re-ignited over issues of opportunity, access, fairness and inequality. Conflict should not be suppressed or pepper-potted over with cheerful architecture; it should be channelled into a healthy re-engagement with class politics.

Inverting the Policy Premise

The case of GMV has thrown up many policy implications for mixed communities. First, the MCI does not stipulate the degree of integration of tenures nor set out design guidelines for the provision of shared facilities (CLG, 2007); in light of their perceived efficacy, pepper-potted communal gardens should be a central requirement for all new mixed communities. But more research is needed to ascertain the exact role these design innovations play in facilitating cross-class interaction. The employment of an ethnographic approach in this study did much to uncover perceived class relations, but more penetrative analytical techniques are required to observe cross-class interactions as they actually occur in these communal environments.

The methodological limitations of this ethnographic study in measuring actual cross-class interaction nevertheless enabled a more probing analysis of residents' perceptions and habitus. One salient feature thrown up by this approach was the perceived importance of children to community integration. Additional research would need to focus on the class relations of GMV children and their parental relationships. Future research needs to be conducted into the effects of on-site mixed schools on cross-class interaction and perceptions of both children and parents. Education policy – principally in regards to catchment areas and selection methods – has positive potentialities for social-mixing. This report calls for more collaboration between these two fields of social enquiry. GMV's innovative use of community online forums throws up a whole host of issues that run parallel to neighbourhood design. Sociological investigations into the quality of social-space created by virtual communities must underpin any attempt to initiate community life via the internet. Online exclusion in GMV appeared to reflect the grossly unbalanced social structure, in which the minority status and lack of representation of social-housing tenants allowed their stigmatisation. It is on reform of inequalities in the housing system that social-mixing research should turn.

Neighbourhood-scale interventions cannot solve systemic inequalities: “especially when they are designed in the same image as the system that makes them necessary” (Lupton and Tunstall, 2008, p.115). The MCI helps perpetuate the neoliberalised land market by compensating for its worst excesses. Social-housing in GMV as elsewhere is partly financed by profits made on private sales. Effectively, the state has outsourced its responsibility of social-housing provision to the market. But in being forced to supply social-housing and internalise the costs, developers have an incentive to minimise quality and quantity. This pressure saw itself expressed in Moat’s careful selection of social-housing tenants and the expulsion of those perceived to threaten GMV’s middle-class habitus and future sales capability. This insidious form of gentrification is the result of bringing social-housing provision under part-private control. A new line in gentrification research must address how corporate marketing and housing association selection techniques shape processes of exclusion.

There is a troubling hypocrisy in housing lower-income-groups through use of the same market processes that act to displace them. It expresses the paradoxical double-think of a policy approach in thrall to neoliberalism: “repairing with the right hand what we ruined with the left hand” (Žižek, 2009). It is part of a national problem in the treatment of land as a commodity to be speculatively bought and sold. GMV’s buy-to-let sales approach is not unique in creating fast-moving markets in which rents are maximised to levels only some can afford. If this proliferates, transience will only become more endemic. A wider political debate needs to address the nature of property-ownership and how profitability in land markets distorts the way people treat their neighbourhoods. This study calls for future research that challenges the ideological grip of neoliberal thought, and questions the deeper economic structures that underpin our hypocritical housing system. To truly tackle socio-spatial inequalities, we need to invert the policy premise: to seek difficult political solutions to pernicious structural problems. As it stands, the MCI is a superficial corrective to inequalities wrought by a system it helps legitimate; dissipating the disadvantaged, and with it, all possibility of mobilising opposition.

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